

JOINT HANDBOOK ON MIGRANTS' INTEGRATION:

A SERVICE DESIGN AND SUPPLY PERSPECTIVE

(JANUARY 2022)

FROM THE 2ND JOINT MIGRATION POLICY ROUNDTABLE

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Disclaimer

All opinions and positions contained in this Joint Handbook on Migrants' Integration are those of the projects concerned and reflect only the authors' views and not those of the European Commission.

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Executive summary

On October 21 and 22, 2021, the six projects named MIICT, REBUILD, NADINE, MICADO, easyRights, and WELCOME, all funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, organized their **second Joint Migration Policy Roundtable**. This Handbook reflects on the two thematic lines common to all the six projects, namely: co-creation, participatory design and multi-stakeholder collaboration on the one hand; ICT or AI based tools and novel digital services for supporting integration on the other. Its contents are the result of the discussion among Roundtable participants, which was articulated in two thematic sessions: the first taking stock of the co-creational dimension to frame the wider issue of service co-design for social integration; the second reflecting on the sustainability conditions of newly developed ICT or AI enabled tools and services. The twin aim was **to identify pitfalls of the current approaches** to migrant and refugee integration as carried out at local level, and **to formulate policy recommendations on how to improve the migrant and refugee integration process within the EU**. In this sense, the Handbook aspires to provide a **strategic toolbox to support reflections in the development of future migration policies at the EU and national levels**.

After a brief Introduction reiterating the global aim of the document and briefly reporting about the proceedings of the first Joint Migration Policy Roundtable held in October 2020 by the same six projects, the remainder of this Handbook text is structured in two main sections, each mirroring a thematic session of the second Roundtable as explained, both co-authored by individual consortium members of the six aforementioned projects.

Section 2 deals with the overarching question: Can service design contribute to social integration? This topic is dealt with according to the following structure:

- Co-design and convergence (responsible project MICADO)
- Community-oriented approaches (responsible project NADINE)
- Co-creation, social design and transformative impacts (responsible project REBUILD)
- Human rights literacy in service design and supply (responsible project easyRights)
- Privacy and data protection (responsible project MIICT)
- Personalization of intelligent technologies for TCNs (responsible project WELCOME).

Section 3 examines the challenges for sustainability of digital solutions for social integration, taking on the following perspectives:

- Bottlenecks in migrants' integration procedures (responsible project NADINE)
- Impacts of socio-technical solutions for migrants' integration (responsible project REBUILD)
- Developing a viable uptake strategy (responsible project MICADO)
- Sustainability of the novel ICT solutions (responsible project MIICT)
- Psychosocial dimensions of AI-supported services (responsible project WELCOME)
- Assessing service accessibility: towards a new standard (responsible project easyRights).

Key lessons learned on the various issues are collected and interpreted in terms of acknowledged pitfalls and evidence-based policy recommendations, representing the "actionable" contents of this Handbook.

Definitions

Migrants. This Handbook uses migrants as an umbrella term and adopts the inclusivist approach to defining migrants as described in the glossary of Migration and Home Affairs of the European Commission¹. Therefore, migrants in this document are mobile persons that reside outside the territory of the State of which they are nationals or citizens of, irrespective of the causes, voluntary or involuntary, and the means, regular or irregular, of this change of residence. This includes individuals who fit into any of these categories: migrant, refugee, or asylum seeker.

Third-Country Nationals (TCNs). According to EU Law, a TCN is any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of the TFEU (Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union) and who is not a person enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code)².

Service design. This term is used to refer to the practice of arranging the actors, infrastructure, communication, and material elements to constitute or improve the quality of service. A service design methodology is characterized by attention to the needs of service users and the capabilities of service providers. In this Handbook, service design tools and methods are commonly established within co-design sessions that allow the study and consideration of the different needs and requirements of involved stakeholders and share the design process with them as experts in the area, to guarantee the sustainability, adoption, and relevance of the proposed services.

Community-oriented approach. The term highlights the role that local communities play in the integration process as well as their responsibility to make integration a smooth process. In this approach, both local and migrant communities are relevant to guarantee the existence of a social landscape of integration.

Social design. The term identifies the socially oriented design aiming to understand societal problems and support positive societal change. Social design can impact the quality of social relations, through the activation of real transformations and changes. Through the design of objects, social design intervenes in society-at-large and on the relationships between the people who are part of it.

Human rights literacy. The term does not only involve human rights related to education or specific professional skills, but also the empowerment of migrants, public officials, members of institutions, civil society, and NGOs in their respective communication, bearing in mind the innate human dignity of any human being.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/pages/glossary/migrant_en

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0399>

Abbreviations

AI: Artificial Intelligence

AIA: Artificial Intelligence Act

API: Application Programming Interface

CA: Conversational Agent

CEAS: Common European Asylum System

DGA: Data Governance Act

DPIA: Data Protection Impact Assessment

DPO: Data Protection Officers

DSA: Digital Services Act

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

IA: Innovation Action

ICT: Information and Communication Technologies

IT: Information Technology

LSP: Local Service Provider

NGO: Non-Governmental Organizations

NLP: Natural Language Processing

PA: Public Administration

TCNs: Third country nationals

UI: User Interface

1. Introduction

1.1 Aim of this Handbook

In the Member States of the European Union (EU) and Associated Countries, **the integration of migrants and refugees remains a challenge for both public authorities and local communities**³. The integration of already established migrants - especially the next generations - as well as “newcomers” such as refugees and asylum seekers, constitutes a serious challenge for our societies and at the same time a unique opportunity to improve our societies in many respects. Obstacles and pitfalls are nonetheless in place, which need to be kept in due consideration.

MIICT, Re-Build, NADINE, MICADO, WELCOME, and easyRights are six Horizon 2020 co-funded innovation actions (IA), which work towards the development of ICT-enabled solutions and toolkits for the implementation of novel inclusion policies and integration support services in collaboration between public administration, private sector and civil society. The six projects apply participatory co-creation methodologies in the development of ICT solutions and follow a collaborative approach involving not only migrants, but also public authorities and other key stakeholders for leveraging the tools and services⁴. In fact, efficient and effective integration of migrants and refugees can only be achieved by clearly understanding the individual situation and the social embedment of the problem. It needs the involvement of key stakeholders such as researchers, public authorities, and civil society organizations as well as the migrants and refugees themselves.

On October 14-16, 2020, the six EU-funded projects organized a Joint Migration Policy Roundtable, structured in three sessions, each focusing on one of their common pillars, namely: co-creation and participatory design; multi-stakeholder collaboration; ICT tools and digital services for supporting integration. These common thematic pillars were described in a consolidated Whitepaper, which was meant to be a strategic input for improving integration and shaping future migration policies in the EU (see **Joint Migration Policy Whitepaper, 2020**, p.8 ff.)⁵.

Following this successful experience, on October 21-22, 2021, the six EU projects organized a Second Joint Migration Policy Roundtable focused on the contribution of service design to integration and the sustainability conditions for the newly developed digital solutions in support of migrants. Two thematic sessions were foreseen in this new Roundtable: the first taking stock of the co-creational dimension to frame the wider issue of service design for social integration; the second reflecting on the sustainability of newly developed ICT or AI enabled tools and services. The two sessions had the common goal of discussing the aforementioned topics and reporting about the key issues emerged in the six EU projects: a number of findings and reflections are presented in this Handbook in the form of recognized pitfalls and policy recommendations nurtured by the lessons learned throughout the implementation of the six projects.

³ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_DT-MIGRATION-06-2018-2019

⁴ For more information of all six projects funded under the same program see here:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/search?q=contenttype%3D%27project%27%20AND%20programme%2Fcode%3D%27DT-MIGRATION-06-2018-2019%27andp=1andnum=10andsrt=/project/contentUpdateDate:decreasing>

⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/migration-whitepaper-new-approach-digital-services-migrants>

This Handbook aims to be an executive document to feed policy decisions and discussions in relation to two operational questions and some associated issues:

- Can service design contribute to social integration?
 - Co-design and convergence (responsible project MICADO)
 - Community-oriented approaches (responsible project NADINE)
 - Co-creation, social design and transformative impacts (responsible project REBUILD)
 - Human rights literacy in service design and supply (responsible project easyRights)
 - Privacy and data protection (responsible project MIICT)
 - Personalization of intelligent technologies for TCNs (responsible project WELCOME).
- Digital solutions for social integration: what are the challenges for sustainability?
 - Bottlenecks in migrants' integration procedures (responsible project NADINE)
 - Impacts of socio-technical solutions for migrants' integration (responsible project REBUILD)
 - Developing a viable uptake strategy (responsible project MICADO)
 - Sustainability of the novel ICT solutions (responsible project MIICT)
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Key lessons learned on the above issues are collected and interpreted in terms of acknowledged pitfalls and evidence-based policy recommendations representing the “actionable” contents of this Handbook.

1.2 The 2020 Whitepaper

In December 2020 the **Joint Migration Policy Whitepaper** was published⁶ as a strategic input for improving integration and shaping the future migration policy of the EU. It focused on ICT-enabled solutions, participatory design and co-creation of those solutions, as well as end-to-end collaboration between the various parties involved in migrant integration in European societies. The Whitepaper was largely disseminated among the competent EU and national institutions and researchers in the domain of “migration and migrants’ integration”. It inspired those Institutions and served as a useful source of information for programs and policy papers at the EU level. One of its most important contributions was the fact that it was used as an important tool at an EU level during the preparation of the “Action plan on integration and inclusion” that was published at the end of 2020. The Whitepaper was created to provide to the key stakeholders and the national administrations in the EU Member States, practical input for future national policies. Descriptions of field experiences were effective in widening the perspectives of inclusion policies by public administration and civil society. The six Migration06 projects highlighted how they worked to increase perceived effectiveness, users’ acceptance, and the adoption potential of the services innovated or digitally transformed.

The 2020 Whitepaper also provided specific policy recommendations at the end of each session that were meant to pave the way for further discussions on how to address the challenges of migrant integration through ICT-enabled solutions. Emphasis was put on understanding migrants’ lives as a prerequisite for defining the scope of their active participation in co-creation and participatory

⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/migration-whitepaper-new-approach-digital-services-migrants>

design sessions, on adopting a wider perspective before addressing specific issues and challenges, and on recognizing the necessity of co-design for trust-building, removing barriers to participation first, and then pushing participatory design ahead.

The crucial benefit of multi-stakeholder collaboration when using ICT to support the integration of migrants was also highlighted. Its value does not only come from being an effective support to the public decision-making process but also to the delivery of digital services to migrants. Moreover, the importance of reiterated public funding to ensure the long-term sustainability of digital platforms facilitating collaboration among stakeholders was reinforced. Publishing success stories of migrants in mainstream media was recommended to ensure smooth and multi-stakeholder integration processes.

The last of the three sessions focused on ICT tools and digital services to support integration. Migrant integration policies require data, statistics, transparent and comparable indicators at the regional and local levels. Learning from the challenges in the field, the six projects highlighted the high potential for overcoming this problem of implementing ICT solutions to support the delivery of public services aimed at integration. To boost the digital transformation of public administration and to support migrants through innovative ICT tools, the Whitepaper recommended to the EC to encourage central governments, local authorities, and other public bodies to guarantee free access to tools data obviously in coherence with relevant national and EU laws and regulations. Also, to boost the integration of migrants, it was suggested to host communities to act as major stakeholders in future research and innovation activities. Providing adequate financial resources to support digital education by public authorities and to promote “interculturalism and multilingual migrant information through ICT” by national laws were the last two recommendations in that session.

Finally, the Joint Migration Policy Roundtable 2020 concluded with six general recommendations mainly addressing how the EC could leverage the innovations and eventually support their future roll-out. These general recommendations can be summarized as follows: 1) support the outreach activities of funded projects; 2) work with practitioners in the field; 3) help the engagement of public authorities; 4) boost the uptake of novel solutions; 5) present the migration projects more widely; 6) bring the projects to broad stakeholder attention.

2. Service design and social integration

2.1. Can service design contribute to social integration?

Access to essential public services in a reliable, affordable, and adequate manner is a key condition for living a life of human dignity and well-being. It also lies at the core of fostering healthy, inclusive, and sustainable societies as highlighted by the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals: *[...] by 2030 ensure that all men and women, particularly the poor and the vulnerable, have equal rights to economic resources, as well as access to basic services, ownership, and control over land and other forms of property, inheritance, natural resources, appropriate new technology, and financial services including microfinance*⁷.

Services as systems fulfilling public needs can be analysed from different perspectives. Among them, essential public services such as water supply, healthcare, or different types of civic or administrative services need to meet certain quality and universality standards to truly serve the whole public and the public interest⁸.

Inequalities related to ethnic and migration backgrounds are evident, such as socioeconomic and spatial segregation (including labour, school, and housing ones), little use of welfare resources compared to autochthonous populations, modest upward mobility processes, deficient recognition of migrant skills and competencies in the hosting societies, discrimination in access to opportunities, concealed racism, etc.

Frequently, it is very confusing and difficult for migrants to understand how to “navigate” in a host country, the offered opportunities, or how to overcome obstacles in accessing crucial resources and basic services. Recent advancements in technological development and services digitization represent an opportunity to enable migrants to better understand the context in which they are in. As highlighted in the report at the seventh Glion Human Rights Dialogue (Glion VII), **an important benefit of digital technology such as artificial intelligence and algorithmic decision making is to improve public service provision**, with positive implications for, inter alia, the right to health and the right to an adequate standard of living⁹.

Furthermore, ICT solutions can also quicken and ease integration processes towards more equal access to services as well as provide flexibilization and adaptation to the needs of migrants that are characterized by an increasing differentiation connected to their diverse backgrounds, skills, patterns, and experiences. Integration goals, at the same time, are challenging ICT development and representing an opportunity toward policy innovation thanks to the experimentation of emerging technological solutions in environments and domains hardly represented in the ICT market demand.

⁷ UN General Assembly Resolution 70/1, Transforming Our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (25 September 2015) UN Doc A/RES/70/1, SDG 1.4, at 15.

⁸ Hesselman, M., De Wolf, A. H., and Toebe, B. C. (Eds.). (2020). *Socio-Economic Human Rights in Essential Public Services Provision*. Routledge.

⁹ <https://www.universal-rights.org/urg-policy-reports/human-rights-in-the-digital-age-making-digital-technology-work-for-human-rights/>

ICT represents only one, although very relevant, dimension of complex service design processes that more and more require the involvement of all relevant actors (migrants, relevant stakeholders including public authorities, researchers, citizens, and local communities, civil society actors, refugee organizations, and migrant associations, research institutions, and IT companies) with the aim to facilitate migrants' integration and develop solutions to ease becoming EU citizens. Focusing on service design and on the role of ICT for developing better and more effective services for migrants according to their actual needs can be considered one of the integration strategies deployed by single countries, regions, or cities.

As many studies and policy documents including the 2020 Whitepaper already highlighted, the adoption of a co-creation approach, and in general, the involvement of local communities and migrants as active participants can play a crucial role in developing solutions for migrants, as it increases the capacity of service providers to cope with the needs of all. Through the co-creative process, various co-design tools and workshops focusing on service design activities, and through combining co-creation and AI technologies, access to public service for migrants can be significantly facilitated.

Moreover, **designing service is a complex task that can play a relevant role in easing the integration process** if it is carried out while being aware of the implications and impacts on migrants. What are the lessons learned from the six Migration 06 projects? What are the key pitfalls and the suggestions we can consider when developing new services or making policies to design and adopt new innovative solutions?

2.2. From lessons learned to acknowledged pitfalls and policy recommendations

CO-DESIGN AND CONVERGENCE¹⁰

As a substantial human-centred activity of the development process, service design needs to ensure that a product or a service is developed based on the needs of its users and allows for high-quality interaction between service providers and users. Furthermore, service design needs to take into consideration the adequate use of available resources, such as human resources, infrastructure, communication, and material components of a service. **A successful service design approach improves the quality and efficiency of service from the perspective of users and providers.**

When designing services for migrants' integration a wide range of stakeholders needs to be considered in the process. This includes migrants, service providers but also any other stakeholder who will be directly or indirectly affected by the service. Key target groups can comprise public administrations (local authorities in charge of migrants' reception), civil society organizations and non-governmental organizations that offer services to migrants, IT providers that manage, maintain, and administer the technical infrastructure used by service organizations, and migrants (asylum seekers and refugees). The knowledge and experience of each target group can feed into the development process to create a minimal viable product or service

¹⁰ This chapter has been mainly authored by the partners of the MICADO project funded under the Horizon2020 program with Grant Agreement number 822717.

An ICT tool that supports migrants’ integration can tackle different domains of the integration process. These domains can include assistance in access to the labour market, information about public health services, guides to education and training opportunities, or provide advice on how to apply for public housing, just to give a few examples. The challenge is hence to decide which part of the integration journey a tool should focus on. By co-creating a tool with migrants and service providers, this decision can be taken to best fit the local needs and existing service infrastructure.

The service design needs to be based on the IT requirements that were agreed upon. These requirements must be measurable i.e. they need to have performance indicators that are aligned with the overall goal of the service and its specific functions.

A robust service design approach needs to be built on co-creation and convergence activities. While key stakeholders and end-users are involved in the co-creation process to ensure that the services meet stakeholders’ demands, the feedback from users’ needs to be analysed and translated into requirements for software development in subsequent convergence workshops. In these convergence meetings, technical partners can discuss software development strategies with partners who work closely with the target groups and understand their needs. The output of the convergence activity is a plan for a unified, broad-based, adaptive solution that addresses crucial local demands and can be implemented by technical partners in a satisfactory way.

There are different methods that can be applied to gather relevant input for service design. One option is to collect input from migrants and service providers and create user stories. **User stories and collected requirements such as descriptions of functionalities and features** are analysed, assessed, and categorized in terms of their criticality and data availability. In the next step, researchers, technical developers, IT experts, and software programmers developed a concept for a minimal viable product based on user requirement analysis. As a result of that activity, a universal solution with selected functions can be devised that is relevant to all the local needs. The Minimal Viable Product then can be tested in the piloting cities, which allows for further (local) iterations of the general solution tailored to specific demands.

Use cases, application scenarios, user stories can be summarized into a logbook for development and uptake. Collaborative discussions and feedback processes can bring invaluable ideas and suggestions in response to specific local user demands. These processes are particularly relevant for the development of apps that are easy to use. If designed carefully, even a complex tool that helps migrants to navigate local bureaucracies can offer an intuitive user experience. One option is to use guided processes that explain complex administrative processes step-by-step.

It has to be noted that while **co-creation approaches deliver vital insights into user needs and preferences**, not all suggestions by all stakeholders can be implemented. Some functions, such as translation of content into multiple languages, cannot be fully implemented due to a lack of resources or because of technical limitations. Here, the challenge is to provide solutions that are compromising between user demands and technical development, that all partners can live with.

Key Lessons Learned

- Involving relevant stakeholder groups from the very beginning of the development is important for successful co-creation processes and paves the way for uptake of services.
- When starting co-creation activities with multiple stakeholders, a robust convergence

methodology needs to be in place to translate stakeholders' inputs into tangible requirements for IT development.

- Parallel piloting in different locations (cities) demands a well-orchestrated pilot and testing choreography.

Pitfalls

- Managing the diversity of languages appears a major issue not only in the practical application but also in the technical development of the ICT tools.
- If local requirements and needs in pilot locations differ in a substantial way, a general (singular) IT solution- or one-size-fits-all solution, might not be feasible

Policy Recommendations

- ICT tools that are developed for migrants should consider their language capabilities and provide content in languages they can master. Provide funds for the development of basic technologies and methods that enable the effective translation of contents in ICT systems for migrant integration.
- Support existing language and translation technologies and propagate their application in future funded projects.
- Propagate standardization of migrant information and data in order to support exchange between organizations on local as well as on (cross-)national level.

COMMUNITY ORIENTED APPROACHES¹¹

An often-neglected aspect of good migrant integration practices is the involvement of local communities and migrants as active participants in the process. While ICT-enabled solutions alleviate some of the burden migrants face when entering and integrating into their host country, becoming a part of the community brings additional stability to migrants' lives.

Displacement leads to disruption in most, if not all, aspects of migrants' lives. A community-oriented approach takes into account the experiences of migrants, their individual needs and struggles, and tackles these challenges through the provision of personalized support. This approach also highlights the role local communities play in the integration process as well as their responsibility to ensure a smoother process. As a result of this approach, both individuals and communities are mobilized and supported, community structures are re-established, and the individual rights of migrants are protected and respected.

The role local communities play in the integration process, as well as the local context itself, determine the integration conditions of migrants. In fact, a multi-stakeholder approach, involving local authorities and civil society organizations, ensures processes that correspond to the needs of migrants. Local authorities are generally the first point of contact for recently arrived migrants. They provide essential services and have a responsibility to guarantee a safe environment and promote long-term integration. On the other hand, complementing the work of local authorities, civil society

¹¹ This chapter has been mainly authored by the partners of the NADINE project funded under the Horizon2020 program with Grant Agreement number 822601.

organizations fill in the gaps local government leaves in the process and provide (more personalized) guidance and support. To this end, local communities can determine the quality and effectiveness of the integration process.

The role of **migrant communities** in the process is often neglected, however, with their feedback, the process can become smoother and ensure long-term integration. This includes asking for and considering their feedback on the integration process and considering their wants and needs, as well as their qualifications. External factors may also determine whether the process will be successful or not. For instance, it has been found that in case a recently arrived migrant is reunited with their family in their host country, the migrant enters the labour market quicker leading to faster employment attachment¹².

Additionally, through community-building initiatives **bringing together the host community and the migrant community**, resources can be unlocked, and a stronger community can be built. These initiatives can tackle the most basic needs of migrants, such as finding adequate housing, which fosters the autonomy of migrants, or they can be more niche, such as cultural exchange between the host and migrant communities.

As a result of a community-oriented approach, the migrants' lives, as well as their economic and social standing, will improve. Furthermore, the social connections within local communities will be enhanced which will ensure faster and better integration for more migrants. This approach also creates increased empowerment for migrants and the local communities, resulting in more resilient communities. Besides considering migrants' feedback on the process, by finding the overlaps and the gaps in the services provided by local authorities and civil society organizations, a less complex integration system can be created that better corresponds to migrants' needs.

Key Lessons Learned

- Considering migrants' needs, qualifications, and feedback on the integration process can improve and facilitate the process better.
- A multi-stakeholder approach to integration fills in the gaps and, consequently, a simpler process can be achieved.
- Through community-building initiatives, more resilient communities can be built inclusive of the host and migrant communities.
- The integration can be achieved more successfully if the process of integrating is considered as an equal action from both sides, the host and migrant communities.
- Societal and cultural context, public opinion, media, and local culture play a significant role in supporting community-based organizations and initiatives.

Pitfalls

- Long and complex bureaucratic procedures.
- Overlap between services, leading to the increased administrative burden
- Lack of Institutional readiness in a host community for wide integration and social inclusion.

¹² European University Institute (2019), Working Paper on 'Refugee integration in Europe since the 'crisis'', for more information see <https://cadmus.eui.eu/handle/1814/62446>.

- Potential conflict and social tensions can arise in the community-led development initiatives.

Policy Recommendations

- Considering migrants' feedback on the integration process would allow for the creation of an integration system that addresses its existing issues from the point of view of migrants, allowing for a more robust integration process that focuses on the needs of migrants.
- There needs to be stronger support for community-building initiatives involving different approaches and activities that bring the host and the migrant communities closer together. These initiatives may range from sharing cultural experiences to providing accommodation to migrants. Community-building practices enhance the individuals' sense of community, lead to better and more efficient integration, and result in a more resilient community including both the host and migrant communities.
- Synergies between stakeholders must be strengthened to fill in the gaps in the integration process and create a less complex system that is easier to navigate. Such a system, built also with input from the migrants, will alleviate some of the burdens on the migrants, resulting in faster and more sustainable integration.
- The complex division and regulation of competencies between the national government, the states, the regions, and the cities must be considered to reduce the bureaucratic complexity and navigation.
- Enabling local residents to benefit from their interaction with migrants can generate larger opportunities for integration and widen welcoming attitudes and behaviours.

CO-CREATION, SOCIAL DESIGN AND TRANSFORMATIVE IMPACTS¹³

Co-creation is widely investigated in the context of the **social function of design** that leads to the creation of artifacts capable of acting on the relationships, structures, and dynamics within western societies. These are digital super-objects that open debates, guide reflections, tackle dominant narratives¹⁴. In particular, the social design approach supports migrants and refugees in life rebuilding and facilitation of access to public services in the host countries.

In this perspective, it is possible to investigate the link between the empowerment of local communities and the design and implementation of AI-based solutions and, consequently, to debate the actual transformative impact of co-creation and participatory design. Social design is focusing on the relation between technology and design and on how to transform work practices since the 50s, trying to challenge the status quo, by means of both novel design of service provision and service fruition strategies¹⁵. Though workplaces and computer systems were at the heart of the Scandinavian

¹³ This chapter has been mainly authored by the partners of the REBUILD project funded under the Horizon2020 program with Grant Agreement number 822215.

¹⁴ Moretti, M. (2019). Design for migration: Nuove pratiche di design verso una società più inclusiva. *Roots-Routes*, 9(29), 1-9.

¹⁵ Papanek, V., and Fuller, R. B. (1972). *Design for the real world* (p. 22). London: Thames and Hudson.

Brock, B. (1977). *Ästhetik als Vermittlung. Arbeitsbiographien eines Generalisten*, hg. von K. Fohrbeck. Köln.

participatory and collective design movement in the past, digital transformation and the service society are on the agenda of today's co-creation practitioners and researchers.

In the co-creation and co-production definitions theoretical and political issues arise, among which: how does the service work? Who is the owner of knowledge of service provision? Who is accountable for the way the service works? **Understandability, ownership, and accountability are key issues of service systems for social integration** and can only be designed with political purposes in mind: is co-creation looking for paternalistic rather than fraternalist approaches? Which kind of democratization is co-production really implementing? And of course, what's the ultimate goal of co-creation action? Is it actually meant to be transformative?

To be effectively transformative, co-creation lets the users share their own life experiences and actively inform design solutions. This knowledge is ultimately elaborated by designers and technologists into the logic and purpose of AI-based solutions. At the same time the co-creation team might value the other way around: not only to target novel users' practices by means of design and technology and to imagine how different the migrants' and refugees' life might be, but also how interacting with migrants and refugees themselves could foster generative processes towards novel research paradigms and methods. By means of continuous iteration and experimentation with interactive technology both the fine-tuning of the technology and the transformative action of the participatory design happens. Continuous iterations between ideas and concepts, and between mock-ups and prototypes experimentation, allows also to empower literacy-at-large in all the participants, at linguistic, cultural, and technological levels.

Literacy at large is conceived as a prerequisite for human contact, social integration, and service development and also represents an objective for removing barriers and integrating diverse user requirements. On the contrary, unbalanced or improper literacy might have drawbacks as weak awareness of duties and rights and thus decreases the possibility for all the participants to co-production to define novel opportunities to innovate social integration.

Key Lessons Learned

- Language literacy is the prerequisite for co-creation processes and requires to be investigated with creative co-design solutions such as visual languages and visual codes. The adoption of visual grammar based on pictograms or on the mixed text and graphic representations allows even illiterate people to understand the context, get aware of the mission of the team, and exchange their ideas.
- In relation to language literacy, sharing the same conceptual models is fundamental for guaranteeing mutual understanding.
- Guidance and mediation might be used in co-creation approaches. The role of the introductory tutorial, video explanation, and interactive prototype ought to be explored for training all the non-designers participants with co-design methods.
- Co-design allows to collect and identify the perspective of a multitude of stakeholders, to build shared decisions, and to find the way to involve at the same time local populations and migrants, and refugees as novel citizens.
- Furthermore, co-design seeks integration instead of separation and does that by means of cooperation between migrants and local communities.
- Cooperation also means to eliminate the distrust and foster acceptance of the society and

this could only be done via a transparent proposition and clarity of objectives and values.

Pitfalls

- Projects and initiatives focusing on migrants’ integration are often designed and implemented with a silo-like approach, undermining the overall effectiveness of any solution, and their actual mid-and long-term sustainability.

Policy Recommendations

- Promote a multi-stakeholder approach involving governments, the private sector, the local community, civil society, public authorities, migrant communities.
- The experimentation cannot be done only with separate groups but should involve the entire actors’ ecosystem. Having all the sectors in society with diverse expectations and needs, solutions for integration might be valuable for scaling up and diversifying accordingly, in order to treat everyone equally.
- Large and extensive experiments would also require observing value, attitudes, and behaviour changes over time.
- Adopt a co-regulation approach by experimenting with a broad range of co-design tools to foster migrant integration and migrants’ active participation in policy design.

HUMAN RIGHTS LITERACY IN SERVICE DESIGN AND SUPPLY¹⁶

Accessing, understanding, and exercising rights are central factors for successful inclusion processes of migrants in the host societies. In this perspective, at least two different instantiations of the broad concept of rights are relevant: (i) irrespective of the type of migration, residence status, and citizenship, migrants are entitled to the recognition and adherence to basic human rights that are universally acknowledged in all free and democratic countries; (ii) the rights of “new citizens”¹⁷- including the right to access welfare services and to exercise civil rights - which are formally granted to regular migrants under the general framework of integration, but depend, in many cases, on the fulfilment of a complex set of rules and conditions. In this “game” **human rights literacy** plays a crucial role.

At the Vienna Conference on Human Rights in 1993, the UN secretary-general stated that human rights constitute a “common language of humanity” (World Conference on Human Rights, Vienna, 1993)¹⁸. They are at the very core of what “humanity” profoundly means. Using this metaphor leads us to say that human rights need to be fully known and understood, and not only declared in laws, treaties and regulations in order to effectively permeate our societies, governments, policies, and actions. People have to know a language to use it and the more they use it, the more they learn it, in a continuous positive loop. So, people need to learn the language of human rights to fully use it and

¹⁶ This chapter has been mainly authored by the partners of the easyRights project funded under the Horizon2020 program with Grant Agreement number 870980.

¹⁷ Even when formal citizenship rights are acknowledged, discrepancies and inequalities between individuals with and without a migrant origin persist.

¹⁸ Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action (1993). Vienna. Retrieved from <https://www.ohchr.org/EN/ProfessionalInterest/Pages/Vienna.aspx>

because of that, there is a crucial topic at all societal levels: literacy on human rights. This was clear since human rights have been recognized as special and different from others.

It is not by chance that the Preamble to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) exhorts "every individual and every organ of society" to "strive by teaching and education to promote respect for these rights and freedoms". The concern was since then that human rights recognition could have a transformative impact on people's lives and on the building of just and robust democracies. Moreover, human rights must be embedded in social practices and give birth, day by day, to new **generative social practices**¹⁹. Institutions are required to ensure that human rights are respected but also individuals are, in this perspective, to be fully involved in the creation and development of human rights-based culture in order to empower them as citizens. As a matter of fact, human rights literacy is a crucial "citizenship tool". Knowing them strengthens both citizens and institutions. It strengthens the work of organizations that operate in the name and on behalf of the public authorities and it strengthens the ability of individuals to interface with the State at all levels.

Although human rights are frequently cited in the day-by-day conversations, they are quite under-researched, also by people that should know them. Students of law and international relations or political science may study human rights in a university setting, but most people, especially those operating on the field and interacting with im(migrants), receive no education, formally or informally, about human rights. Even at the European level, the public administration staff are not sufficiently aware of the impact on human rights of their policies.

Human rights literacy has been studied and investigated largely in countries experiencing gross and persistent violations of human rights; they often design human rights education programs and other measures to combat human rights violations²⁰. A South African research project titled "Human Rights Literacy: A quest for meaning" explored the student-teachers' conceptualization ontology of human rights and meaning of human rights values; it concluded that "human rights literacy, as understandings of dignity, equality and freedom as both rights (legal claims) and values (normative action) within horizontal and vertical applications, aid rights-based education towards transformative action and an open and democratic society"²¹.

Human rights emerge from everyday social practices, and their articulation can also establish new and innovative practices. Therefore, the term "human rights literacy" involves not only human rights related to **education** or specific professional skills, but also the **empowerment** of migrants, institutions, public officials, civil society and NGOs in their respective communication, bearing in mind the innate human dignity of man. Two of the main characteristics of a human rights-focused

¹⁹ Ventura, C. A., C. Rubens, M. S. Gutier, I. Mendes (2016). Alternatives for the enforcement of the right to health in Brazil. *Nursing Ethics*, 23(3): 318–327.

Ventura, C. A., I. A. Mendes, S. de Godoy, L. Fumincelli, M. C. Souza and V. D. Souza (2019). Perceptions of Brazilian nursing faculty members regarding literacy of human rights related to health in nursing undergraduate programs. *BMC International Health and Human Rights*, 27: 19-27. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12914-019-0213-7>

²⁰ Becker, Anne; Annamagriet de Wet and Willie van Vollenhoven (2015). Human rights literacy: Moving towards rights-based education and transformative action through understandings of dignity, equality and freedom. *South African Journal of Education*, 35(2): 1-12.

Hamel, R.E. (1994). Indigenous education in Latin America: policies and legal framework. In Skutnabb-Kangas, Tove and Robert Philipson (Eds.) *Linguistic Human Rights. Overcoming linguistic discrimination*, Mouton de Gruyter: 271-288.

Roux, C.D. and Du Preez, P. (2015). Human right literacy: a quest for meaning. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.2310.4160

²¹ Becker, Anne; Annamagriet de Wet and Willie van Vollenhoven (2015). Human rights literacy: Moving towards rights-based education and transformative action through understandings of dignity, equality and freedom. *South African Journal of Education*, 35(2): 1-12. Quotation from page 1.

public policy are people’s empowerment and compliance with international human rights standards. Both aspects are guided by the central element of human rights that is human dignity. In this sense, freedom —in the form of self-determination— is one of the key aspects in the development of the concept of human dignity. Likewise, international standards carry a set of rights that appeal to superior, higher needs of human beings, beyond the satisfaction of very basic needs, i.e., freedom, equality, peace, etc.

The very recent **EU Regulation 2021/2303²²**, approved after the Policy Roundtable, introduces important obligations for member states as per human rights literacy that already covers some of the policy recommendations provided below and considered relevant to be included at national, regional, and local levels.

Key Lessons Learned

Although in 2005 the *World Programme for Human Rights Education* of the United Nations was launched to tackle the need for specific training on this issue and human rights literacy is considered as a fundamental asset for different subjects, be they individuals or organizations, **human rights education programs with a focus on vulnerable groups and public services have been implemented only to a limited extent.**

In several countries²³ training activities on human rights have been addressed exclusively to police forces with national or international competence. However, this kind of training is only compulsory for missions in sensitive areas or are otherwise taken up on a voluntary basis. Although in some cases training plans include personnel dealing with vulnerable groups (children, women, minorities, indigenous peoples, etc.) or being involved in activities challenging the gender perspectives, the absence of quantitative reports on trained staff suggests a weak commitment and implementation in this respect.

Of the known measures, only a small proportion of institutions and persons that are actual contact points for migrants, for accessing public services, and for service delivery are covered. Still, it is evident that service provision requires a full awareness of involved human rights as well as of risks associated with denied rights once they are undermined by obstacles in services access.

If we consider the plurality of actors that are indirectly and directly relevant for the design of and for the delivery of/access to public services, a complex landscape of actors unfolds consisting of multiple stakeholders from different areas of policy, administration, non-profit organizations, public service sectors and individual networks and communities of migrants.

Pitfalls

Some recurrent pitfalls are to be considered at the level of service design and provision in relation to human rights literacy and to the key scope of assuring human rights respect at all levels of the services creation process.

Awareness and empowerment

- Migrants are predominantly weakly aware of being the owner of inalienable human rights; also, when they are fully aware they retract from exercising them as they often feel not

²² Regulation (EU) 2021/2303 - formally signed by the co-legislators on 15 December 2021 - concerning the establishment of a European Union Agency for Asylum (EUAA).

²³ See: <https://www.ohchr.org/EN/Issues/Education/Training/WPHRE/SecondPhase/Pages/SecondphaseEvaluation.aspx>

being in the conditions for rights reclamation.

- Many services operators are fully aware that services do have impacts on human rights and also can list most of the negative implications consequent to the failing of the service journey completion but still, they almost uniquely gain these competencies thanks to every day “fieldwork!” which makes their knowledge and preparedness incomplete and inadequate in any case but especially from the point of view of legal implications.
- Human rights violations often occur because of the discretionary practices, especially of street-level bureaucrats and/or operators involved in providing services to migrants.
- Local language knowledge (by migrants and professionals dealing with them) can be an obstacle in acknowledging basic rights.
- Migrants frequently must rely on “mediators” (be they professional ones like lawyers or informal ones) to enforce their basic rights.

Education and training

- In public administrations, literacy on human rights is mostly developed in the field, in the sense that operators, whether they are top management or front office staff, had minimum opportunities to participate in training courses on human rights or issues related to migrants.
- Training on the field is very often developed by operators thanks to roles played in public administrations or to immersive voluntary experiences that allowed them to develop a relevant understanding and sensitiveness towards migrants’ problems; no structured training introduces big uncertainty in the service response across Europe especially in relation to those services and procedures that define the way migrants get potentially integrated.
- The lack of systematic training also worsens the already existing conditions of scarce alignment of laws and regulations across the EU deepening migrants’ uncertainties and fragility and exposing them to the risk of basic rights violation.
- Legal implications of critical knowledge on, and understanding of, human rights may be hard to evaluate and consider. Nevertheless, they are crucial and require specialized skills and competencies at very different levels of services supply side with special attention to the roles played by translators and cultural mediators supporting migrants in the interaction with public authorities.
- Training on human rights is important to build safeguarding policies in organizations and must be tailored to different contexts and trainees. Public authorities and private actors frequently don’t have the same educational needs and gaps.
- Quite often local operators don’t master basic language skills to work with migrants and serve them.

Service design and supply

- Long timing in accessing services and completing integration procedures is not clearly understood as a form of infringement of basic human rights by civil servants; this specific topic is, on the contrary, identified as one of the most evident forms of human rights negation by many actors providing services and support to migrants.
- Services are not explicitly “human-rights oriented” as well as they are not “children” or “gender” oriented.

- Service interfaces (digital or not) fail in making available clear services pathways; they also require too many steps/clicks, do not usually have multiple language options including migrants' mother-tongue language; finally, service usability is not assured to people owning only basic digital skills.
- The language barrier is widely recognized as an impediment to the completion of service journey worsening migrants' vulnerability and undermining their basic rights; nevertheless, the offer of multiple language functions is rarely considered as a key point of attention in service design and supply at the levels of ICT, documental and staff provision.
- While it is widely shared that ICT solutions can facilitate access to information and increase the transparency and accessibility of the activities of public institutions and governments, they can be misused for disinformation, data falsification and manipulation so implying the necessity to consider that new technologies generate demands for a new generation of human rights that arise the need of specific and innovative research and professional practices.

Policy Recommendations

Key obstacles for migrants to exercise their rights is the complexity of bureaucratic procedures; this is particularly challenging if migrants do not have any previous knowledge or experience with such administrative systems, and even more so if they have no or limited literacy in the script and language of the host country. Access to welfare services, especially for these groups, often requires face-to-face interactions and a strong, not discretionary, street-level bureaucratic system. As a consequence, **improving the knowledge of basic human rights is a precondition for a more inclusive society.**

Policy measures are necessary to be developed targeting two different, rather complementary goals: i) deepening the human rights literacy of actors involved in service design and provision; ii) embedding human rights-oriented solutions in ICT enabling services, especially those to be used by migrants.

Deepening human rights literacy

- make human rights literacy a strategic cultural, educational, and policy goal for the integration of migrants in Europe;
- provide human rights-related training to all operators and organizations acting in origin countries to make migrants capable to exercise their rights;
- guarantee training on human rights for key actors in service provision for them to gain competences on consequences of human rights infringement and abilities to navigate human rights as drivers for solving procedural issues;
- make legal implications related to human rights infringement a focal point of training on human rights;
- reduce the aleatory of competencies developed through fieldwork experience as a unique form of provision of a human rights literacy;
- support the development of human rights-based training with adequate economic resources but also with organizational ones;
- control should be adequately granted of the compliance of the practices of National Public Administrations and of National Law Enforcement Authorities (the Police) to the fundamental rights, as defined in the EU Charter on Fundamental Rights;

- develop an adequate and compulsory training framework on human rights for public servants at national, regional, and local level.

Embedding human rights-oriented solutions in ICT enabled services

- design ICT-enabled solutions with user-friendly interfaces which inform and reassure migrants about their rights and obligations;
- make ICT interfaces simple and usable by simple basic digital skills;
- make service ICT interfaces available in multiple languages (migrants' native language included) available in both vocal and textual modes;
- supply through ICT solutions service pathways clear and easy to understand;
- develop a framework for digital rights that encompasses all platform stakeholders, including - but not limited to- designers, users, and shareholders.

Finally, policies should generally target specific human rights issues when specifying and fixing service quality standards:

- access and completion of service-related procedures must be short and should not affect integration processes like those related to housing, job search, family creation, schooling, security, or to health provisions;
- services' pathways have to be understood easily thanks to a minimum provision of clear and accessible information provided before and during the interaction with services themselves;
- homogeneity of service procedures and access modes across EU countries and cities is a way to reduce the discretion of service operators and guarantee equal access to human rights.

PRIVACY AND DATA PROTECTION²⁴

Data protection is a human right. On a European level, it is enshrined in Article 7 (“Respect for private and family life”) and Article 8 (“Protection of personal data”) of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union²⁵. Furthermore, both privacy and security of personal data are extensively protected by EU Regulation 2016/679, also known as the General Data Protection Regulation (“GDPR”)²⁶. The GDPR has a wide-reaching application and applies in all cases of processing of “personal data” which it defines as “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person” that includes “name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person” (Article 4(1) of the GDPR). Furthermore, it also covers all EU organizations regardless of whether the data itself is being processed outside of the EU, as well as non-EU organizations that, however, process the personal data of EU citizens (Article 3 of the GDPR). Article 5 covers the principles of processing which are the cornerstones that must be

²⁴ This chapter has been mainly authored by the partners of the MIICT project funded under the Horizon 2020 program with Grant Agreement number 822380

²⁵ European Union, *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*, 26 October 2012, 2012/C 326/02. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A12012P%2FTXT>.

²⁶ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), OJ L 119, 4.5.2016. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

complied with in every instance of personal data processing, especially in the context of ICT-enabled systems and solutions. Article 6 clarifies the applicable grounds for processing and the rights of the data subjects are covered under Chapter III of the Regulation. Article 25 establishes the principles of data protection by design and by default as overarching and which must be duly considered as early as the planning of the development of ICT-enabled systems.

It is also important to take the following proposals into account, as they pose important implications for further strengthening privacy and data protection across the EU in the near future:

- The Data Governance Act (DGA)²⁷, introduced as part of the European Data Strategy, proposes to strengthen the data sharing between the data subjects and any users of that data through secure data intermediaries/data-sharing service providers. In addition, through the implementation of additional measures that are intended to ensure full compliance with the GDPR in respect of personal data protection, the proposal aims to establish better control overall for the data subjects.
- The proposal for a Digital Services Act (DSA)²⁸, as part of the package including the Digital Markets Act, aims to improve transparency and accountability for online platforms by introducing due diligence obligations for them. It proposes additional measures to be taken by Very Large Online Platforms, such as conducting risk assessments. Also, the interplay between the DSA and the GDPR would be of key importance for privacy and data protection considerations and, while the DSA would uphold the GDPR principles it also elaborates further on certain aspects, such as clarifying what is perceived as “transparent”. Thus, the DSA may be considered as building on the GDPR even further and introducing even stronger protection for data subjects.
- Another pending proposal, the Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA)²⁹, envisages a complete ban on certain AI systems which manipulate vulnerable individuals, are used for social scoring or run real-time remote biometric identification systems in publicly accessible spaces for law enforcement. It also defines and provides for the regulation of high-risk AI systems and also lays down strengthened transparency requirements.
- Last but not least, the proposal for an EU ePrivacy Regulation³⁰ which will repeal the current e-Privacy Directive³¹, proposes to enhance the privacy protection of electronic

²⁷ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European data governance (Data Governance Act), COM/2020/767 final. Available at:

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020PC0767>.

²⁸ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on a Single Market For Digital Services (Digital Services Act) and amending Directive 2000/31/EC, COM/2020/825 final. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2020%3A825%3AFIN>

²⁹ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (artificial intelligence act) and amending certain union legislative acts, COM/2021/206 final. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021PC0206>.

³⁰ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the respect for private life and the protection of personal data in electronic communications and repealing Directive 2002/58/EC (Regulation on Privacy and Electronic Communications) COM/2017/010 final - 2017/03 (COD). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52017PC0010>.

³¹ Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications), OJ L 201, 31.7.2002, p. 37–47. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=celex%3A32002L0058>.

communications through introducing clearly defined rules in this respect and thus complementing the provisions of the GDPR.

Key Lessons learned³²

The key lessons learned from a legal and ethical point of view focus on three interconnected dimensions while developing and implementing ICT-enabled systems, as well as their testing and use by human participants. These include legal, human rights, and data protection considerations respectively, and must be duly incorporated at each step of the development process. Such a comprehensive and all-encompassing approach was found to work quite well in ensuring that all safeguards are put properly in place to provide adequate and sufficient protection of the data subjects' rights, especially in cases where a vulnerable group of people, such as migrants, is concerned.

In terms of data protection³³ more specifically, the following aspects were focused upon:

- Importance of implementing data protection **by default** and **by design**;
- Following the six principles of the GDPR, namely that:
 - the data processing must be on a lawful basis, fair and transparent;
 - purpose limitation of the processing must be observed;
 - data minimization must be ensured;
 - the processing must be accurate;
 - storage limitation must be defined;
 - integrity and confidentiality must be followed;
 - the data controller and data processor must have accountability in respect to all principles listed above.

Data Protection Impact Assessment

The carrying out of a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) when developing ICT environments to be used by migrants appears especially useful in terms of monitoring whether the developed platform or tool is compliant with all data protection considerations. Also, ensuring that the DPIA is observed along time and updated in terms of the risks encountered and corresponding measures to mitigate/eliminate the risks that are in place, is considered a good practice. The regular provision of an updated DPIA makes sure that any new challenges encountered from the technology developed are handled in a timely manner.

Joint Collaboration and Cooperation

Strict collaboration and cooperation among all the actors involved in the ICT development also including those whose having a role in the ICT product exploitation is valuable, in order to develop an overall picture for all implications that the Platform has. This requires working closely and regularly with the developers so that all aspects in relation to the technical development are made

³² Similar challenges regarding ethics, privacy and data protection are equally experienced when creating digital tools. One example of how these challenges were overcome is provided below from the MIICT project. This can provide a blueprint for future initiatives wishing to embark on research using co-creative methods to create ICT solutions to migrant integration.

³³ These data protection protocols are from the IMMERSE platform created in the MIICT project. They can serve as a blueprint for other researchers working in the area to ensure that full data protection considerations are put in place when creating ICTs to aid migrant integration.

transparent, as well as with the actors interacting with migrants in the pilot countries so that the practical perspective is more easily captured, understood, and duly taken into account. Indeed, such a joint effort provides for a comprehensive data protection framework to be developed and also for the bridging of any existing gaps in expertise between legal and technical experts—that is to say, from a legal point of view to understand the risks and considerations in terms of technical aspects and from a technical point of view to then adequately implement these considerations into practice.

Pitfalls

Common pitfalls in terms of the development of ICT-enabled systems include:

- Not having sufficient measures in place to ensure that the required express and informed consent has been obtained from the data subject prior to the data processing.
- Reactive and not proactive actions by the data controllers in terms of existing risks to the personal data of data subjects. Data controllers must anticipate risks before they take place and not wait until they have already materialized.
- Services offered based on various individual characteristics, such as age, gender, and nationality which may increase the risk of discrimination.
- Excessive processing of personal data that is not necessary to be provided for the purposes of using the ICT-enabled system and the services offered through it.
- The personal data provided is used beyond the stated means and purposes and the technical and organizational measures in place to ensure the security of the data are not reviewed regularly as the external threat environment and technology changes.
- Relevant information is not adequately communicated to the data subjects due to language difficulties which affect the right to information.
- The “once only” principle for the processing of personal data by public bodies is not adhered to.

Policy Recommendations

The recommendations below have been developed from a legal and ethical standpoint to ensure that a full data protection framework is built in ICT-enabled systems for migrants' integration:

- ICT-enabled systems must process data without causing any negative effects to the users.
- Only the data that is necessary for the provision of the service must be collected, following a pre-defined scenario and applying the “once only” principle where data must be collected only once at the different stages and where such information is relevant. The same information is not to be asked again when it comes to the provision of another service requiring the same or parts of already input information.
- Data controllers must periodically revise the collected information in order to keep it up to date.
- Users must be informed about their right to withdraw consent through ICT-enabled systems and must have the opportunity to exercise that right through it.
- ICT-enabled systems must automatically inform data controllers, migrants, and data protection authorities about cases of data breaches without delay.
- Data controllers should conduct data protection impact assessments whenever a new service is planned to be integrated into the ICT-enabled system.

- The controller shall consult the supervisory authority prior to processing when the processing would result in a high risk for the rights and freedoms of users.
- Data controllers must appoint Data Protection Officers (DPO).
- Users must be informed through the system of the processing activities taking place.
- ICT-enabled systems must provide information to migrants about their rights in the processing of personal data and the ways to exercise them, following a layered approach.
- The system must inform users for how long the personal data will be stored or at least the criteria of how this period is determined.
- The presented information through the system must be free of charge.
- All information must be presented through the system in a clear and understandable way.
- The ICT-enabled systems should enable their users to exercise their rights as data subjects through the system.
- All collected data must go through pseudonymization and encryption processes for better data security.
- The system must ensure the availability, confidentiality, integrity of the processed information.
- In cases of data breaches, the system must be able to restore access to personal data.
- Establishment of data protection policy and taking steps to make sure that the policy is implemented.
- Regular security checks to be carried out to evaluate whether the taken technical and organizational measures are up to date.
- The ICT-enabled system needs to be interoperable with relevant e-governance systems and eID schemes.
- When the provided services include automated decision-making or profiling the system must provide information to the users about the nature and method of that processing.

PERSONALIZATION OF INTELLIGENT TECHNOLOGIES FOR THIRD COUNTRY NATIONALS³⁴

Third Country Nationals (TCNs) who arrive in Europe are required to go through complex registration procedures, have to learn the language of the host country, find employment, etc. Very often, they are overburdened and need more background information, some guidance (or coaching) and training. However, it must be taken into account that the **needs depend on the educational, cultural, and social background of each TCN**. Therefore, personalized support is needed. On the other hand, over the last decade, significant advances have been achieved with respect to intelligent ICT-based technologies, and, more notably, with respect to personal assistants or conversational agents. This calls for the use and further development of these technologies in the context of TCN reception and integration in the EU.

Key Lessons Learned

- Third Country Nationals (TCNs) are expected to complete a number of multiple-stage reception and integration procedures, in which some of the stages presuppose the

³⁴ This chapter has been mainly authored by the partners of the WELCOME project funded under the Horizon2020 program with Grant Agreement number 870930.

successful completion of the preceding stages; often, the documentation they have to deal with is more complex (and specific) than documentation migrants moving from one European country to another have to handle;

- TCNs do not form one homogeneous group; they have diverse educational, cultural, and social backgrounds.
- Each TCN has its own communication skills, its own unique experiences, its own needs and values, and its individual capacities and capabilities.
- If we furthermore take into account that TCNs, as a rule, do not speak well the language of the host country and are not familiar with its social and cultural norms, let alone the bureaucratic procedures, the need for personalized assistance of each individual becomes obvious. Given that personalized assistance of TCNs by authorities and civil society sector is heavily conditioned by the availability of human and financial resources, intelligent technologies in terms of conversational agents (CAs) that assume the role of a personal assistant can be designed and provide support to the public administrations and civil society in the whole process.

Pitfalls

Common pitfalls can be observed on both extremes of the personalization of the TCN-targeted services:

- Intent to acquire and process sensitive personal data (such as, e.g., health conditions) of the TCNs. This might result in optimized assistance, but implies significant critical issues related to trust, data protection, and also technical complexity.
- Intent to generalize the services across such features as age, gender, country of origin, etc. This simplifies the technical realization, but does not meet the personalization needs of the TCNs.
- Intent to cover too many services and thus be too ambitious for the given time and financial frame (which will necessarily lead to superficial support in all of them).

Policy Recommendations

- Support empirical studies that identify the concrete needs of TCNs during their reception and integration in the countries of the European Union and align these needs with concrete ICT-based services.
- Support the development of service-specific CA solutions (i.e., coaching of TCNs how to prepare and how to act during a job interview); they will be more beneficial than generic solutions.
- Support targeted Natural Language Processing (NLP) applications that cover the analysis and synthesis of languages spoken by TCNs (it is not enough to focus on machine translation as it is not enough to focus on selected majority languages).

3. Sustainability of solutions and social integration

3.1. Digital solutions for social integration: what are the challenges for sustainability?

The sustainability of ICT tools that facilitate migrants' integration is inherently dependent on a multitude of factors. These are both positive and negative, ranging from the design of the tool and the information and services provided therein, to the acceptance and uptake in the communities where such tools are introduced and implemented. **Sustainability is also linked to the national, regional, and local context.** Delivering new forms of innovation for facilitating migrants' integration and strengthening the social integration through digital solutions carries out different challenges and poses several questions such as how to ensure access to innovation outcomes to end-users as well as the **usability of the solution for migrants** and also for the service providers. How to assess the impacts of socio-technical solutions for migrants' integration and guarantee the inclusion of privacy, legal and technical considerations as a way to foster sustainability? Is the technology involved compatible and easy to integrate with the existing service components for example municipality ecosystems? And eventually to what extent does the solution address the issue of long-term sustainability?

This session presents interim findings from work in progress at the six Migration 06 projects and discusses policy-related issues on sustainability and the adoption of solutions and tools of social integration. As a result of the implementation of inclusion policy, ICT-enabled solutions and toolkits may have elevated the task of public administration, local authorities to deliver and manage better and customized services. Facilitating communication and access to services through ICT solutions helps improve migrants' autonomy and inclusion. Moreover, it helps to define efficient integration tools and implementation at the local level for sustainable inclusion of migrants and effective public perception of migration. The contribution of the six projects on this topic demonstrates the reusability or scalability of developed solutions at the European level and their potential to ensure long-term sustainability as well as take-up by identified users.

This section lays out a number of key lessons learned on how to approach sustainability of digital solutions and enumerates challenges and pitfalls to overcome when managing migration, welcoming, orientation, and integration using technological means from the different angles of social integration and challenges for institutional sustainability. Detected problems include surviving bottlenecks in migrants' integration procedures, insufficient analysis of the impacts of migrants' integration (and of the costs of non-integration), limited consideration of the psychosocial dimensions of migrant profiles during the development of ICT or AI-supported integration services, and the lack of an assessment standard for service accessibility. We also propose a number of policy recommendations that may assist in overcoming some of those hindering factors as well as improving the known favourable conditions to a wider uptake of the novel ICT solutions.

3.2. From lessons learned to acknowledged pitfalls and policy recommendations

BOTTLENECKS IN MIGRANTS' INTEGRATION PROCEDURES³⁵

Migrants' integration has been and still is a challenge across the EU. This is proved by the EU-level documents, which attempted to harmonize the various approaches followed and offer guidelines in the integration process, and often remained unenforced for very long time³⁶. The crucial stages of integration policy enforcement can be identified as the arrival and application for asylum status, the verification of information, interviews and decisions, access to housing, and labour market integration. The stages, highlighted here for their strategic role in the integration process, are complemented by other steps, most of which are interconnected in many ways. The approaches to identified key stages of integration differ across the Member States, creating various bottlenecks and heterogeneities across the EU. Nevertheless, the integration process should be considered as a whole as opposed to standalone stages or approaches in order to improve and enhance the efficiency of integration.

Arrival and application for the asylum status

According to the Asylum Procedures Directive³⁷, the application process should be completed within six months, or nine months in specific cases, following the submission of the application. However, in practice, delays are common in many Member States. For instance, in some countries, the average waiting period to even get their status registered can last as long as 12 months. Delays can be due to a lack of harmonization across the EU regarding the conditions that asylum seekers must fulfil in order to gain access to the labour market, a lack of administrative capacity to process large amounts of applications, and an increased administrative burden on the employers hiring asylum applicants.

Decision and appeal

Evaluating asylum applications is a national competence, although guidelines are available at the EU level. As a result, national legislation prescribes the maximum length of the process, however, delays occur quite often, especially when large amounts of applications are filed at the same time. Although a short procedure may seem appealing and cost-efficient, the quality of the process should not be neglected, as a higher quality process reduces the number of appeals filed after a decision has been made. The time needed for reviewing the appeals and the specificities of the process are a national competence as well. The evaluation of appeals often lasts longer in the Member States where judicial authorities are in charge of the procedure. The delays applicants face during the decision and appeal (if applicable) stages negatively affect their prospects in other key aspects of the integration process, including access to housing and to the labour market.

Housing

Housing is another key aspect of the integration process, upon which other steps in the integration process rely, such as access to education, employment, and healthcare. However, due to limited

³⁵ This chapter has been mainly authored by the partners of the NADINE project funded under the Horizon2020 program with Grant Agreement number 822601.

³⁶ See as examples: the 'Common European Asylum System' https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/policies/asylum_en European Commission, (2020) as well as the 'Action plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027'. <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/news/the-ec-presents-its-eu-action-plan-on-integration-and-inclusion-2021-2027>

³⁷ Directive 2013/32/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 on common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=celex%3A32013L0032>

housing options and overflowing reception centres, migrants often face inadequate living conditions. The bottlenecks related to housing also include a shortage of affordable housing in the area and the limited budget capacities of cities.

Labour market

Gaining access to the labour market is a decisive factor in migrant integration, as it is connected to other aspects of integration, such as access to language training, housing, etc. The shorter the waiting period, the better will be the economic integration of migrants. On the other hand, longer waiting periods negatively affect migrants’ motivations, and a lack of long-term permits negatively affects the prospects of finding a stable job as well. Another aspect connected to access to the labour market is the insufficient capability of speaking the local language, which is also connected to accessing social networks and building social capital.

Although the bottlenecks connected to the different aspects of the integration process are varied, ICT tools can mitigate these issues, for instance by providing comprehensive information in a user-friendly format in many languages on what documents are needed, or providing information on migrants’ rights, and giving them quick access to local networks to enable social integration.

Key Lessons Learned

- Approaches to migrant integration are different across the EU. For instance, there is a lack of harmonization on the conditions asylum seekers must fulfil to gain access to the labour market.
- The main bottlenecks connected with each key aspect of the integration process are varied and can differ between the Member States.

Pitfalls

- Delays in key aspects of integration, including registration as asylum seekers and gaining access to the labour market.
- Long administrative delays negatively affect the integration of migrants and their prospects.
- Lack of access to information for migrants.
- Difficulties and conflicts may arise in the process of integration.

Policy Recommendations

- Through exploring digital solutions, multiple bottlenecks can be alleviated or even eliminated. ICT-enabled solutions, complemented by additional changes and more harmonized approaches across the EU could, for instance, shorten administrative delays which is one of the biggest hindrances in migrant integration.
- The lack of availability and accessibility of information is an obstacle for most migrants, however, ICT tools could provide more accessible information. This would reduce some of the burdens on migrants and lead the way to a smoother integration process.

IMPACTS OF SOCIO-TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS FOR MIGRANTS' INTEGRATION³⁸

Assessing the impact of socio-technical solutions such as those developed by the six projects present at the roundtable can be of great help in fostering outputs' sustainability. Indeed, by showing in qualitative and quantitative terms the benefits of the solutions developed, the chance to find further (financial) support for their improvement and upscaling increases considerably. Certainly, assessing the impact of socio-technical innovations in the field of migrant inclusion also represents a challenge as no standardized approach exists yet.

Talking about impact means answering questions like "What is the difference a project makes?" and "For whom?". Impact assessment is a way to assure transparency and increase accountability but is also a way of increasing reflexivity within a project or within an organization: it is a tool for learning and improving development activities and outputs. More importantly in this context, impact assessment can also be a tool helping innovators better communicate the benefits of the solutions developed to potential investors, up-takers, and other stakeholders.

The areas considered while assessing the impact of socio-technical solutions for migrant integration are the social, economic, political, and technological ones. Each dimension is articulated in several sub-dimensions which include, but are not limited to: impact on education and human capital; impact on health; impact on social capital; impact on employment and economic empowerment; impact on service efficiency; impact on digitalization and technology usage; impact on trust in local institutions and impact on policies.

In order to map all the potential impacts of socio-technical projects and take into consideration all outputs, it is important to consider the impact on different stakeholders, mainly: migrants and refugees, Public Administrations (PAs), and other actors acting as Local Service Providers (LSPs) and the whole society.

Clearly, the final expected impact of socio-technical projects, as those presented at the Policy Roundtable this document is the output of, is the inclusion of migrants in the host society, being this a multifaceted and still debated concept. They are expected to increase migrants' integration by improving access to and increasing the effectiveness of already-existing services. The areas of impact and dimensions considered for assessing the impact on migrants and on PAs and LSPs are:

- Impacts on migrants:
 - social impact: education and human capital; health; citizenship and social capital
 - economic impact: employment; access to bank and financial services; economic empowerment;
 - political impact: digital democracy; trust in host country institutions; civic participation;
 - technological impact: digital literacy; technology usage; information asymmetries.
- Impacts on LSPs and PAs:
 - social impact: workforce human capital; collaboration and networking; workforce working condition;

³⁸ This chapter has been mainly authored by the partners of the REBUILD project funded under the Horizon2020 program with Grant Agreement number 822215.

- economic impact: efficiency; internal working routine and work processes; accountability and transparency
- political impact: policies; institutions;
- technological impact: services’ digitalisation; access to information.

By gathering data during development and testing activities, it is possible to describe in qualitative and quantitative terms the impact on the above mentioned dimensions. Data can be of help in better describing the value generated by outputs and their potential if scaled up from pilots and proofs of concept to actual large-scale implementation.

In parallel to this analysis, it is also useful to consider **the cost of non-integration of migrants for the host society** so as to be able to show - in financial terms - the opportunity space for investing in socio-technical solutions for their integration. In doing so, an in-depth analysis of the different and complementary costs that the EU Member States incur as a consequence of integration failure has been carried out, including, e.g., cost of irregular migrants’ imprisonment, cost of unemployment benefits, cost of migrants’ healthcare, cost of low educational performance for migrant students, cost of discrimination and cost of the reception. The analysis shows that the costs for a migrant that is not properly integrated into the host society can be as high as 52,000 Euro per year for a single person. An important disclaimer on the above figure is needed: the analysis conducted maps the cost of non-integration with reference to the Italian case and can be used only as a reference for reflection and further analysis on the situation in other EU countries.

The assessment of costs of non-integration deserves further analysis, but it clearly shows how investments in integration - including investments in socio-technical tools - can be of great relevance for the host countries and can result, even, in a cost-saving for governments.

Key Lessons Learned

- Considering different stakeholders, in different countries when assessing the impacts of socio-technical solutions for migrant integration is really important as the differences among contexts are high, and customized solutions emerged as the most valuable in terms of adoption and long-term sustainability.
- Mixing qualitative and quantitative methods in assessing impacts helps in better communicating to different stakeholders and potential up-takers: for some the economic aspect is crucial while for others more soft, social, and story-telling-based descriptions are better welcomed.

Pitfalls

- It is still difficult to find comparable data on migrant integration across EU countries. Moreover, within the same country, regional and local data are often missing or not comparable. The lack of standardized approaches in monitoring the integration phenomenon lead also to the lack of historical series of data that are crucial in mapping the impact of policies and investments.
- Often, when data are available, they are not provided as open and FAIR data, this is a shortcoming in terms of re-use of available data and research progress.

Policy Recommendations

- To support the long-term sustainability of projects like the ones presented in this roundtable it would be advisable to have dedicated programs at the national and at EU level for supporting the research-to-market phase of the innovation produced. Innovation actions, even when they proved to deliver effective solutions, need further economic investments for their outputs to reach the market and be further customized to final users' needs.
- PAs should be better supported in collecting data on the status of migrant integration: assessing the impact of project results and of their outputs can help prioritizing this goal, which would also provide useful information for better navigating the multitude of projects and initiatives active across EU countries.
- Besides this, a program of technology transfer, with ad hoc experts, should be offered to policymakers to support them in taking decisions on socio-technical solutions adoption.

DEVELOPING A VIABLE UPTAKE STRATEGY³⁹

An effective **uptake strategy** needs to assess the key social, economic, and technical environments in which the IT solution will be operating. Potential risks and hurdles to uptake need to be evaluated and addressed. Sustainability principles guiding responsible use of resources and limiting the environmental burden need to be part of this strategy. An uptake and sustainability strategy or plan should offer:

- general measures and guidelines, which may apply to any location in which the technical solution will be taken up;
- specific strategies for local uptake that take into consideration local demands, existing IT infrastructure and processes, management structures, and responsibilities of different institutions in the domain of service provision.

ICT solutions need to address three levels of sustainability, i.e., the sustainability of usage, technical maintenance, and sustainable development.

- 1) The end-users should be trained and get familiarized with the solution, so they can use it independently and incorporate the usage into their daily routine.
- 2) The technical operability and the continued administration of content presented on the IT tool need to be managed in a sustainable manner. The responsibility of continued administration and maintenance needs to be assigned to an agency (the organization that provides services to migrants and/or an external IT provider).
- 3) ICT solutions are living products and require sustainable development. Software development needs to keep abreast of technical innovations and changes in the environment in which the software is embedded.

³⁹ This chapter has been mainly authored by the partners of the MICADO project funded under the Horizon2020 program with Grant Agreement number 822717.

To ensure these three levels of sustainability, specific processes and activities need to be prepared. The critical question is who takes over the management of each level. One possibility is to delegate the responsibility to one institution. However, this strategy does depend on the institutional networking capacity of the ICT developer in terms of personal resources, technical infrastructure, and expertise. Relevant is to refer to the different actors who were already involved in the co-creation process. Software developers may form a central caretaker hub - a technical core team that ensures the long-term open-source development of the software solution. Delegation of responsibilities for sustainable uptake also needs to be linked to sustainable business planning and a strategy to secure funding for continuous development, maintenance, and development of the IT tools.

A comprehensive guide to the uptake of IT solutions should be developed which includes a summary of the purpose of the uptake activities, a roadmap for local activities, and a clear management structure that outlines the responsibilities of each stakeholder (partner) involved in the uptake process. The guide needs to present the general plan for uptake and sustainability and provide input on how these strategies can be adapted and implemented in different local contexts. Finally, the guide needs to include strategic mid-term and long-term goals of an uptake strategy.

Key Lessons Learned
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A generic uptake and sustainability plan is needed that outlines uptake demands and requirements for usage, operations, and technical development. ● Generic uptake plans need to be modified and translated into local uptake plans that meet contextual conditions. ● End users and uptake entities should be involved in the planning of uptake strategies from the very beginning of the ICT development work.
Pitfalls
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Without the constant monitoring of (administrative) changes on the organization level of institutions and organizations being the potential uptakers of the solution, uptake activities may miss the target. ● Due to institutional changes, previously stated uptake commitments may be taken back, or substantially altered. ● While the planning for a sustainable uptake strategy happens during the project life-cycle, uptake activities are rarely continued after a project end.
Policy Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Financial support may be useful to target the uptake of ICT solutions that have already proven to be effective in integration of migrants. ● Relevant to the uptake may be more a capillary information sharing of success stories and solutions. ● Promotion of networked experiments of ICT solutions among different communities and institutions may be part of a targeted uptake strategy. ● The European Commission may consider the provision of supportive financial frameworks that enable future usage, operations, and technical development beyond projects' runtime (e.g. operation funds).

SUSTAINABILITY OF THE NOVEL ICT SOLUTIONS⁴⁰

Novel ICT solutions that deploy matchmaking tools linking migrants and service providers together need to be made sustainable according to many aspects.

First, delivered information must be up to date, reliable, credible and officially endorsed by public sector organizations. This is a crucial requirement, challenged by the twin facts that information is not static and the user needs change across time. Also, translations of relevant documents and information need to be sensitive to dialects and constantly maintained and available in real-time. This implies that continual monitoring of the platform needs to be undertaken by stakeholder groups including the migrants themselves, who can give valuable feedback on the utility of the information contained in it.

Another important aspect for developers to consider is accessibility. Any ICT social innovation tool is to be designed for accessibility and not to deepen the digital divide that may occur on grounds such as educational level, language skills, gender, age, previous exposure to digital devices, and income⁴¹, whereby ordinarily marginalized groups are excluded⁴². ICT solutions, therefore, need to be accompanied by training opportunities and the provision of free WIFI to users.

Another issue concerns value. A well-documented social innovation risk is failure to provide value to the targeted audiences⁴³, especially in the long term, where user retention and the expansion and/or narrowing down of the services offered start playing a crucial role in determining whether a technological tool survives the test over time or becomes obsolete.

One more aspect for policymakers to consider is ethics, as migrants are vulnerable and can be at risk of exploitation, so the administrator of a platform must veto all links and information.

Another factor enhancing sustainability obviously comes from securing long-term funding for the maintenance, expansion, and implementation of later-stage learning outcomes in relation to social innovations of the ICT type⁴⁴.

Key Lessons Learned

Accessibility

At the primary level, technological solutions must ensure that they are accessible to their targeted end-users. A robust, but appropriate technical infrastructure is necessary, such that it is responsive

⁴⁰ This chapter has been mainly authored by the partners of the MIICT project funded under the Horizon 2020 program with Grant Agreement 822380

⁴¹ Farbenblum, B., Berg, L. and Kintominas, A. (2018). *Transformative Technology for Migrant Workers: Opportunities, Challenges, and Risks*. New York: Open Society Foundations.

⁴² Bock, A. K., Bontoux, L., Nascimento, S., and Szczepanikova, A. (2016). *The future of the EU collaborative economy*. JRC Science for Policy report.

⁴³ Virketyte, A.; Wiklund, I. (2019). *The Creative Process for Digital Social Innovation in the Context of Migrant Integration* [PhD dissertation]. Jönköping: Jönköping University.

⁴⁴ Farbenblum, B., Berg, L. and Kintominas, A. (2018). *Transformative Technology for Migrant Workers: Opportunities, Challenges, and Risks*. New York: Open Society Foundations.

Virketyte, A.; Wiklund, I. (2019). Op. Cit..

Teberga, P. M. F., and Oliva, F. L. (2018). Identification, analysis and treatment of risks in the introduction of new technologies by start-ups. *Benchmarking*, 25(5), 1363–1381.

to different devices and operating systems, as well as a user interface design (UID) that can accommodate both desktop and mobile versions without great divergences. Accessibility also relies on the user base being able to access a device, through which to make use of the particular ICT tool, and being capable of operating this device at least on its basic functionalities.

One of the key lessons learned is to ensure that within the different pilot locations support sessions are offered in order to ensure that specific groups - such as those that are illiterate and the visually impaired - are able to use the ICT tool. Another lesson is to ensure that the platform is available on mobile phones and mobile apps since they are acknowledged as the preferred medium for accessing information and services by migrant users⁴⁵. This would ensure that migrants can access vital services whilst on the move.

Responsiveness

Also, at the foundational level stands the challenge of responsiveness, understood here as the capability to reflect the current needs and wants of end-users, and the potential to continue doing so in the future, as those needs and wants change and evolve. It is vital for an ICT tool to offer a wide spectrum of relevant information and services that bring practical value to end-users and are of everyday utility. The creation of a one-stop-shop approach is important in enabling migrants and service providers to save time and be more independent and proactive in their own integration journeys.

Reliability

Reliability is intrinsically tied to the credibility of content. The challenge of verification, fact-checking, and ensuring security and trust must be foundational to the design and development of any ICT platform. Due to the highly sensitive nature of information additional care must be taken to validate that information and check that it is truthful and corresponds to official sources, and services offered are genuine. An additional concern arises from the fact that migrant end-users constitute a vulnerable group and do stand at a heightened risk of exploitation and abuse. All privacy and data protection risks need to be examined to ensure migrants are not put at risk.

Opening the platform to the public or up-scaling for commercial use would mandatorily entail the allocation of resources for the verification, validation, and fact-checking of information, services, and users (e.g. service providers).

Pitfalls

Tailored service provision

In the early stages of co-creation, the need for customization arose hand-in-hand with the realization that end-users in different pilot countries act in different environments, have different

⁴⁵ Nedelcu, M. and Soysüren, I. (2020). Precarious Migrants, Migration Regimes and Digital Technologies: The Empowerment-Control Nexus. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1369183X.2020.1796263>

Farbenblum, B., Berg, L. and Kintominas, A. (2018). *Transformative Technology for Migrant Workers: Opportunities, Challenges, and Risks*. New York: Open Society Foundations.

<https://www.opensocietyfoundations.org/publications/transformative-technology-migrant-workers-opportunities-challenges-and-risks>

Gelb, S. and Krishnan, A. (2018). *Technology, Migration and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. London: Overseas Development Institute.

<https://odi.org/en/publications/technology-migration-and-the-2030-agenda-for-sustainable-development/>

needs and preferences, and must be provided with different services. One important issue related to this aspect of tailoring is the need to provide adequate languages and translations that take into consideration the local context and region. Another important factor is to enable the ICT solution to add new modules and functionalities, whilst keeping services and information updated and modifiable in the various migrant languages.

Marginalized groups

Some ICTs may lead to the exclusion of marginalized groups such as women, the elderly, unaccompanied migrants, and migrants who are illiterate or visually impaired. The creation of local hubs or information points could enable migrants who are less comfortable with using ICT tools to access information and services, build their digital skills, and acquire new qualifications. This would enable those migrants who fear being tracked by the authorities to use the ICT solution with the support of trained staff. The fear of digital surveillance is a concern that can jeopardize the success of any ICT solution.

Take-up and ownership

Project-based social innovations carry the inherent characteristics of being time- and resource-constrained and being capable of reaching a finite number of beneficiaries before activities come to an end⁴⁶. This is why the post-project take-up and the assumption of ownership over any innovation remain challenges worth addressing.

Policy Recommendations

Engagement and ownership

Multi-stakeholder engagement in all stages of ideation, creation, and implementation helps reap the fruits of continuous learning from a spectrum of points of view. The encouragement of cross-organizational communication in the formulation of migration and integration policies at any level is to be done paying due attention to meeting migrants' needs through ICT tools, as well as conventional methods, especially in the COVID-19 and post-pandemic realities.

We recommend that the EC strongly encourages governments, local governance structures, and public bodies to take ownership of novel ICT solutions that have proven successful in the field and have garnered support from non-governmental organizations and service providers, working with migrants, as well as migrants themselves, after the end of project activities, should those solutions be project-based. In supporting and commissioning ICT tools for migration and integration, governments should ensure consultation with and feedback from non-governmental organizations working with migrants, as well as migrant communities and sub-groups within those communities. Good working relationships and stable collaborations with Internet providers and mobile service providers are also of utmost importance. The sustainability of existing ICT tools relies upon the ongoing and long-term value creation for migrant end-users, regardless of how their needs and preferences change in time. Hence, ensuring funding and human resources necessary for the provision of this value is of crucial importance.

Digital education and inclusion

It is highly recommended that the digital education of migrants and the breaking down of the

⁴⁶ Codagnone, C. and Kluzer, S. (2011). *ICT for the Social and Economic Integration of Migrants into Europe*. JRC Scientific and Technical reports. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

digital barriers that many migrants face are recognized as common goals among all EU Member States. The process of digitalization should not remain divorced from the issues of social inequality, marginalization, and exclusion that vulnerable groups such as migrants often encounter in their daily lives. Hence, the EC must continue to promote and build support for a rights-based understanding of ICT infrastructure and the Internet, emphasizing the value of equal treatment and non-discrimination.

Furthermore, it is recommended that the EC supports governments both methodologically and financially in providing such education and locally countering the digital barriers while offering fair and adequate opportunities for NGOs working with migrants to benefit from renewing or expanding their existing ICT infrastructure, where this is needed, so that they can provide access to ICT tools for migration and integration to their beneficiaries on their premises.

Finally, it is suggested that the EC considers targeting policies and measures that engage specific sub-groups of migrants who are at higher risk of being marginalized and excluded from accessing and benefiting from ICT tools, such as illiterate women, the elderly, those living in extreme material deprivation, and those with low or no education. Gender mainstreaming and acknowledgment of intersectionality are vital in this respect. Support for governments and NGOs that work with such groups is essential in overcoming the socio-economic barriers before their full-fledged inclusion and successful integration. Without continuous capacity-building and skill-development among both migrants and professionals working with migrants, the sustainability of novel ICT tools for migration and integration could be compromised.

Building confidence and trust

It is recommended that the EC urges member states to refrain from unjustified and indiscriminate violations of freedom of communication and the right to privacy of correspondence of migrants, which extend to their online activities as well. On the other hand, data security in an environment of increasingly frequent cyberattacks against online public infrastructure is a matter of growing concern. Protection of personal data mechanisms and adequate and effective remedies in cases of breaches ought to be established across the EU with a particular emphasis on vulnerable groups and users with lower awareness of online threats and risks.

It is important that end-users have trust and confidence when accessing and utilizing ICT tools, not only from the viewpoint of being able to easily complete tasks and resolve issues (which is readily addressed by digital education), but also of having the perception and knowledge that their data and interactions are kept confidential and secure. This would reduce the scepticism and raise the motivation in benefiting from digital solutions for migration and integration.

Investing in and fostering (through targeted policy and legislation) stable progress in the area of personal data protection, cybersecurity, and cyber rights is recommended to achieve the goal of ICT tools' sustainability.

Funding for sustainability

Of all the challenges and pitfalls discussed in this section of the Handbook, lack of funding for scaling, bringing to maturity, and implementing changes in technology on the basis of later-stage learning remains the most considerable constraint to the longevity and sustainability of platforms. Funding is also crucial for ensuring that comprehensive and reliable test and end-user feedback can be collected and analysed in a consistent manner over time.

Thus, the assumption of ownership over a given technological tool for migration and integration at

the end of a project-based life stage is not solely a question of stakeholder willingness and support, but also of available finance. Hence, it is recommended that the EC and the member states act to financially secure the long-term exploitation of successful digital social innovations either through designated funding or amendments in national budgets that free up resources to be pooled in this direction.

Importantly, funding is the single defining factor behind many of the good practices and lessons learned presented here – for instance, migrant digital education and bridging the digital barrier are highly dependent upon the availability of human and financial resources to implement these activities. Therefore, governments ought to make room for this set of integration measures in their general migration budgets, while NGOs should be given ample opportunity to apply for and gain the funding that allows them to carry out tasks related to migration and integration via digital tools.

PSYCHOSOCIAL DIMENSIONS OF AI SUPPORTED SERVICES⁴⁷

Leaving one's home country and migrating to a different one is often complex and stressful, related to events before departure, during travel and transit, and after arrival. Refugees in particular have often been exposed to stressful events such as wars and other forms of armed conflict, persecution, discrimination or natural disasters⁴⁸. Upon arrival in the host country, third-country nationals have to cope with the need to adapt to a new society, often with a new language, different climate, and majority culture. Their minority status puts migrants and refugees in a disadvantaged position, prone to discrimination and increase vulnerability. These difficult processes and experiences often raise concerns about the fate of their families, regardless of whether the families travelled with them or stayed in the country of origin or transit. Additional challenges may involve learning the language of the host country, searching for employment, getting acquainted with the health and social services, managing the bureaucratic requirements for obtaining permission to reside in their new community. A key issue is the fact that there is uncertainty about how long they can stay in the country and that creates a lot of stress and difficulties. The threat of being homeless, deported, detained, and/or suffering from long waiting times until their status is finally determined is a common problem among many MS.

The number and complexity of the necessary administrative procedures are considerably higher than those of the usual procedures that the locals need to follow routinely, and if we consider that even locals often feel overstrained, so do Third Country Nationals (TCNs), at a much higher rate. The role of social and governmental services and civil society has been fundamental for the successful assistance of TCNs, but there is a need for more support.

In view of the fact that intelligent human-computer interaction technologies and more recently, Artificial Intelligence (AI) have become an important element in a number of different applications, including, e.g., information delivery, education, and coaching, simulation and training, entertainment, and media, these technologies appear to be an ideal instrument to support the

⁴⁷ This chapter has been mainly authored by the partners of the WELCOME project funded under the Horizon2020 program with Grant Agreement number 870930.

⁴⁸ World Health Organisation (2018) *Mental health promotion and mental health care in refugees and migrants' Technical guidance*. https://www.euro.who.int/data/assets/pdf_file/0004/386563/mental-health-eng.pdf?ua=1

reception, integration, and coaching of TCNs in Europe. However, the vast majority of these technologies are realized as a “one-size-fits-all” solution, which means that they assume a predetermined average profile of their users with respect to their needs, background, and capacity. Even if we assume that all TCNs need to go through the same procedures and thus require assistance on the same matters, their needs are different because of the large variation of their social, cultural, and educational backgrounds.

Furthermore, **forced migration backgrounds often imply high levels of psychological distress, deep personal traumatic experiences, often dangerous journeys full of privation, and a profound disillusion upon arrival in the host country**, which may affect the mental and psychological equilibrium of the individuals concerned. In particular, through the process of adaptation to a new environment, and because of their past experiences of discrimination, migrants are more prone to psychological stress than the average, which across time may lead to symptoms of depression or emotional burden as they strive to adapt to the receiving context conditions.

All the six projects involved in this Handbook preparation faced similar challenges related to the psychosocial status of TCNs when designing AI-supported integration services. The following table can provide a blueprint for future projects on how these challenges can be taken into account during the preparation of ICT and AI-based tools for TCN reception and integration in the EU.

Key Lessons Learned
<p>Key lessons learned in terms of the development of ICT systems include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asking and involving the target groups (migrants, asylum seekers, and refugees) from the beginning of the design of any process and within all phases of the implementation of a project until its evaluation and not only in pilot phases. • Harmonizing the language between technology and human sciences. • Taking into consideration the several dimensions of a TCN’s experience when discussing how to automate integration procedures and design/develop specific tools for their support.
Pitfalls
<p>Common pitfalls in terms of the development of ICT systems include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not taking into account the specific characteristics of the target groups when trying to match them with needs. Target group’s needs must be recorded correctly in order for the services offered to be adapted to various characteristics, such as age, gender, religion and language, to avoid increasing the risk of discrimination. • Developing ICT solutions from scratch and trying to implement them in a vacuum, without considering the differences in each country might end up in a non-applicable system. It has been observed that host countries may be unable to support TCNs as their systems are not ready, and remain unprepared, especially after the change in the migration flows of the period after 2015.

- There is a special issue in the area of integration in the employment domain: an appropriate match of the individual's profile with his/her own special qualitative characteristics is rarely made. This automatically results in a profiling that is poor or negative for the TCN.

Policy Recommendations

- It is highly important to consider the socio-psychological dimensions (that are taken into account by professionals) during the interaction with TCNs. The analysis of psychosocial backgrounds is of primary importance in the context of AI-supported services: it reveals a large variety of social and cultural backgrounds, different (very often traumatic) life experiences, expectations, etc. Moreover, each TCN has his/her own communication skills, own traumata, needs and values, formal or informal educational background as well as individual capacities and capabilities.
- AI-supported services cannot be a “one-size-fits-all”. To ensure adequate service provision, there is a need to identify and differentiate the most distinctive psychosocial features and take them into account in technology development and implementation.

ASSESSING SERVICE ACCESSIBILITY: TOWARDS A NEW STANDARD⁴⁹

The quality of integration policies varies widely across European countries. In spite of the standards set out by EU and international law, citizens still experience disparities within and between Member States and cities, and such disparities worsen migrants’ conditions as they are not treated fairly and equally wherever they apply for support.

In a report made by Eurocities in 2018⁵⁰ it was clearly stated that most cities have performed (and are still performing) significant efforts to promote citizenship and equal access to rights and services by the migrants through implementing dedicated measures, such as: in some cases, setting up new bodies in charge of implementing inclusive policies or **introducing monitoring mechanisms against discrimination**; in other cases, **adopting new guidelines and plans for equality**; or **investing in accessible services** offered in many languages and tailored to the specific needs of migrants and refugees.

EUPAN, the informal network of the European Commission and Directors General responsible for public administration in the EU Member States, has largely promoted the adoption of standards for quality management in the public sector, including for the measurement of satisfaction in service usage as a proxy for compliance; these initiatives are certainly relevant, especially given the positive impacts that the use of standards has generated in both the public and the private sectors.

Citizens’ charters have been largely used since the 1990s and recently confirmed (see the EUPAN network report of 2018⁵¹) as a good way to develop or adopt standards, or quasi-standards. Their

⁴⁹ This chapter has been mainly authored by the partners of the easyRights project funded under the Horizon2020 program with Grant Agreement number 870980.

⁵⁰ https://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/3rd_Integrating_Cities_Report_October_2018_FINAL.pdf

⁵¹

implementation varies significantly across countries, due to the different legal systems in place. So while some charters are enforced by law, others are more informal commitments and/or statements of principle. Also, several countries report challenging experiences in measuring service compliance with the target levels set out in the Charters, so they either use the feedback received from users or rely on general commitments to improve quality, without the recourse to specific monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. The contents of these Charters across countries present a high degree of similarity (although with some differentiations) for the commitments made: on-time delivery targets, a positive attitude of public sector workers, non-discriminating actions, transparent and accountable behaviours, inclusiveness and openness of government etc. Access to public services is promised in a multi-modal fashion (e.g. by post, online, by phone and in-person). Mechanisms are put in place for the general public to provide feedback on public service delivery and there are intentions to use this feedback to improve public service development in the future. Formal complaint procedures are set out as well as contingent processes covering the cases where standards are not met.

In general “all countries consider that it would be worthwhile to explore further the potential benefits/possibilities of developing some form of common non-binding public service delivery standards on an EU level, but there are different views on the scope of the needed cooperation, which need to be agreed upon. Still, most countries point towards the development of common principles for quality of public service delivery across the EU, which will not be binding for the Member States, but will offer them a benchmark and guidelines when adopting their national standards” (EUPAN, 2018, p.5).

Generally, the common principles for quality service delivery are related to

- **listening to and understanding** the customer;
- **designing and implementing** policies and services that meet citizens’ expectations;
- providing timely, high standard and **easily accessible services**; and,
- **being accountable** when people (citizens/users) become part of service provision.

User centricity is generally acknowledged as a key concept in service (re)design for both the private and public sector innovators. In the private (for profit) sector, the equivalent concept to User Centricity is Customer Centricity. This posits that **the customer must ‘come first’**, i.e. a company should put all its efforts into troubleshooting its customers and creating a product or service that is really of value for them⁵². Following this train of logic, the analytical unit for a hypothetical assessment of Customer Centricity is not a specific good or service, but the company that produces it. For instance, a customer centric provider should integrate customer experience programs throughout the organization itself⁵³ or use feedback collection methods and tools as well as customer satisfaction metrics to ground its decision-making⁵⁴. Indeed, as noted by some scholars⁵⁵ “the

https://www.eupan.eu/wpcontent/uploads/2019/02/2018_1_BG_Citizens_Charters_and_Public_Service_Delivery_Standards.pdf

⁵² F. Adrodegari, D. Bonetti and N. Sacconi (2017). A Framework to assess the level of Customer Centricity in Manufacturing Companies. Paper presented at the RESER Conference, Bilbao, Spain.

⁵³ Hayes B. E. (2013). TCE - Total Customer Experience, Building business through customer-centric measurement and analytics. Lexington, Kentucky: Business Over Broadway.

⁵⁴ Manning, H. and Bodine, K. (2012), *Outside in. The Power of Putting Customers at the Center of Your Business*, Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, Boston, MA.

⁵⁵ Adrodegari et al. (2017). Op. Cit.

transition from a product centric approach to a customer centric one is very complex and requires a transformation process that covers all the organizational aspects of the company". This is a very interesting research and practical domain, but obviously not transferable as such to the public sector, which is eminently subject to the rule of law in the daily management of its current affairs. In fact, while the collection of inputs from government service users in the form of satisfaction metrics has been customary since long, particularly in association with the implementation of quality standards⁵⁶, it remains true that a government body or agency demonstrating their propensity to listen to the opinions of citizens and/or businesses cannot be considered user-centric only because of that.

With the 2017 **Tallinn Declaration on eGovernment**⁵⁷, 32 Member States narrowed the focus on 8 basic principles (aka standards), the fulfilment of which in a context of digital public service delivery or existing service digitization should ensure that citizens and businesses are genuinely placed at the centre of the newly built or redesigned public services. These 8 principles are reported below.

When interacting with public administrations and using digital public services, citizens and businesses should expect:

- *Digital Interaction*
 - *To have the option to digitally interact with their administrations*
- *Accessibility, security, availability and usability*
 - *That the services are made more accessible (including findable) and secure and can be used by all in a non-discriminatory manner, with appropriate assistance available upon need.*
 - *That the principles of universal design have been applied to the setting up of the services and that the websites are simple to read and easy to understand.*
 - *That the authenticity of digital public services is secured and can be recognised in a clear and consistent manner.*
- *Reduction of the administrative burden*
 - *That public administrations make efforts to reduce the administrative burden on citizens and businesses, namely by optimizing and/or creating digital processes and services where relevant and possible, and by offering personalised and pro-active services.*
 - *Not to be asked to provide the same information to public services more than once, in due respect of data protection rules and regulations.*
- *Digital delivery of public services*
 - *That public services can as much as possible and appropriate, especially upon request of the user, be fully handled online, including the provision of any evidence required to obtain a right or fulfil obligations.*
 - *That the status of service delivery can be checked online where relevant.*
- *Citizen engagement*
 - *That digital means are used to empower citizens and businesses to voice the views, allowing policy makers to collect new ideas, involve citizens more in the creation of public services and provide better digital public services.*
- *Incentives for digital service use*
 - *The barriers to use digital public services should be effectively removed, including by extending and promoting the benefits of, for example, higher confidence, speed, effectivity and reduced costs to individuals who are able to use them.*

⁵⁶ See e.g. M. Wiśniewski (2001) Using SERVQUAL to assess customer satisfaction with public sector services, In *Managing Service Quality*, 11(6): 350-388.

⁵⁷ For more info https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/document.cfm?doc_id=47559

- *Protection of personal data and privacy*
 - *That the handling of personal data respects the general data protection regulation and privacy requirements in the EU and national levels, when applicable informing citizens about the use and storage of their personal data and allowing citizens to access and ask for the correction and deletion of personal data, where appropriate.*
- *Redress and complaint mechanisms*
 - *That redress mechanisms are available online and that citizens and business have access to complaint procedures online, while also in other available channel(s) of their choice.*

These 8 standards add further dimensions to Principle #6 (of 12) of the European Interoperability Framework (EIF), which generically underlines the importance of analysing, understanding and reflecting users' needs and requirements during the design and development of public services in accordance with their expectations. As a matter of fact, Online Availability and Online Usability have been considered for quite a long time the two key components of User Centricity. The former refers to the existence of an electronic channel for public services either through a portal or standalone. The latter looks at the overall user experience of support, help and feedback functionalities, ease and speed of use. This is the situation created at the EU level with the eGovernment Benchmark Framework 2012-2015⁵⁸. More recently, and notably after the publication in April 2016, of the eGovernment Action Plan for 2016-2020, Mobile Friendliness (and accessibility) was also added, to reflect the fact that while the use of mobile Internet has become widespread, only 1 in 3 European public websites at the time was designed to be 'mobile friendly'⁵⁹.

Mainstreaming a user-centric approach to the evaluation of the quality of public services for migrants can and should constitute the next immediate challenge for EU policy making: this would enable at the same time, the harmonization of basic service delivery irrespective of the place of fruition and a concrete progress towards User Centricity and Interoperability of this special category of government services - differentiating themselves not because of a fundamental heterogeneity but only due to the particular nature of served beneficiaries.

Key Lessons Learned

- Although accessibility has been up to now considered one among other service quality issues, it is evident that it represents a relevant goal for migrant's integration. The way to the adoption of a quality standard for public services, and more specifically for public service accessibility, is paved and the challenging perspective of integration is making it an urgent issue across EU countries.
- The absence of a shared accessibility standard makes the accessibility itself a deep differentiated quality of services creating disparities and inequalities across Europe.
- Differences in service laws and in-service governance models across EU countries make the adoption of a service accessibility standard a complex challenge: considerations are needed for the level of decentralization of service provision.

⁵⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/sites/digital-agenda/files/eGovernment%20Benchmarking%20method%20paper%20published%20version_0.pdf

⁵⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/eu-egovernment-report-2016-shows-online-public-services-improved-unevenly>

- Shared understanding and guidelines on citizens’ needs and expectations may improve the efficiency of the public sector across Europe and increase transparency and accountability so widening citizens’ knowledge about, and confidence in, public services.
- Existing service quality standards have been introduced and used discontinuously across Europe and developed with scarce knowledge of the users’ experience: accessibility should take into account the users’ experience for it to become an integration measure.
- New standards are required that are more focused on User Centricity and Interoperability of these services.

Pitfalls

Linguistic offer in service provision is crucial but does not represent the unique obstacle in service access.

Discretionary in the interpretation of service accessibility and the ways to guarantee it across service sectors and across countries introduces disparities and inequalities and represents a significant obstacle to migrants’ integration.

Bureaucratic complexity of service procedures represents an infringement to information rights and makes service access difficult and, more critical, open to failures. Differentiation in accessibility modes improves service quality but at the same time widens the bureaucratic complexity of the service thus challenging its accessibility.

Compliance with basic human rights and human rights literacy represents a critical challenge in service provision especially when services do have deep impacts on citizenship and cascade effects on other services and rights.

Policy Recommendations

Improving the accessibility of public services is surely crucial to migrants’ integration in Europe; it also represents an opportunity to homogenize European citizenship and reduce the administrative stress of the public sector. The creation of a standard to assess service accessibility would reduce disparities and unequal legal implications consequent to eventual failures in administrative service and procedure accomplishment.

In compliance with the User Centricity principle, such a standard could and should be a collection of minimum requirements for enforcing the informational rights of foreign migrants and refugees entering the European Union legally. It would provide a common basis for the harmonization of public services to migrants and refugees across Europe, under the perspectives of quality of communication and effectiveness of information delivery. It should embed at least the following three characteristics: coverage, coherence, and outreach.

Coverage

The assessment standard should differentiate the various dimensions in which a service is articulated and provide a series of reference points (levels or steps) by which progress in accessing that service can be calibrated; also, it should be able to sense whether public services are designed to consider many possible use cases in different and complex situations including those that often occur when migrants are involved.

Coherence

As services are interfaces between citizens and their rights, the assessment standard should be able to detect the internal contradictions among service delivery process components, which may establish conditions for possible discriminations to guarantee equal service access (and therefore access to rights) to all beneficiaries.

Outreach

The assessment standard should verify that a service scope, rules, and procedures are clearly formulated, promptly available, and readily comprehensible to its prospective users; all the beneficiaries, migrants included, should be able to complete their service journeys in autonomy (without external support) avoiding the risk to fail due to lack of understanding.

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